

Supplementary materials

Dynamic sustainability assessment tool. Case study of green biorefineries in Danish agriculture

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S1. Pigs' production submodel

In the pigs' production submodel, four main stocks *Piglets*, *Growing Pigs*, *Gilts & Slaughter pigs*, and *Sows* are included that simulate the lifecycle of pigs in a conventional farm, see Figure S1.

Figure 1. Stock and flow diagram for the submodel of the conventional pig farm.

These major stocks and flows simulate changes in the number of sows, piglets, and growing pigs. The purpose of the model is to maintain the needed number of sows per year in production cycle that can produce the demanded number of piglets. The total number of sows change with the annual increase in the total production of piglets and with the changes in the productivity of

production cycle. Further the flow of piglets is divided into exported piglets and piglets kept for fattening and slaughtering.

There are two flows for sows' replacement – one internal and other external. Internally the part of the gilts is used to displace sows. In this model, the constant number of sows is affected only by external factors. These external changes are the expansion of the conventional pig farms based on the historical data for the period of 2010-2018, with an average growth of 0.32 % per year [1].

Table S1 shows the names of auxiliary variables and corresponding assumed numerical values and references for pigs' production submodel.

Table 1. Assumed values for auxiliary variables in pigs' production submodel.

Variable in the model (correspond to the variables in Figure S1)	Numerical value used	Assumption	Reference
Amount of life piglets born per sow per year (as initial value)	28.0 piglets/sow/yr	Average historical data for number of conventional pigs in Denmark in 2009	[2,3]
Ratio of sows' replacement	51.3 %/yr	Equal distribution among all sows	[2,3]
Share of demand changes for piglets	0.32 %/yr	Historical data for number of conventional piglets in farms in Denmark in 2008-2018	[1]
Share of died gilts & slaughter pigs	3.30 %/yr	Equal distribution among all gilts & slaughter pigs	[2,3]
Share of died weaners	3.10 %/yr	Equal distribution among all weaners	[2,3]
Share of exported piglets (as initial value)	25.0 %/yr	Average historical data for number of conventional pigs in Denmark in 2009	[1]
Share of sows died	11.0 %/yr	Equal distribution among all sows	[2,3]
Share of sows slaughtered	41.3 %/yr	Equal distribution among all sows	[2,3]
Sows (as initial value)	1034695 animals	Historical data for number of conventional pigs in Denmark in 2009	[1]

The corresponding equations used in the pigs' production submodel are given below in Table S2.

Table 2. Equations used in the pigs' production submodel.

STOCK:

$$\text{Sows (t)} = \text{Sows (t - dt)} + (\text{Sows change rate due to external factors}) dt + (\text{Gilts replacing sows rate}) dt - (\text{Sows mortality rate}) dt - (\text{Sows slaughtering rate}) dt$$

INIT:

$$\text{Sows} = 1034695$$

INFLOWS:

$$\text{Sows change rate due to external factors} = \text{Sows} * \text{Sows needed to cover the demand for piglets}$$

$$\text{Gilts replacing sows rate} = \text{Sows} * \text{Ratio of sows replacement}$$

OUTFLOWS:

$$\text{Sows slaughtering rate} = \text{Sows} * \text{Share of sows slaughtered}$$

$$\text{Sows mortality rate} = \text{Sows} * \text{Share of sows died}$$

STOCK:

$$\text{Died sows (t)} = \text{Died sows (t - dt)} + (\text{Sows mortality rate}) dt$$

INIT:

$$\text{Died sows} = 0$$

INFLOW:

Sows mortality rate = Sows * Share of sows died

STOCK:

Slaughtered sows (t) = Slaughtered sows (t - dt) + (Sows slaughtering rate) dt

INIT:

Died sows = 0

INFLOW:

Sows slaughtering rate = Sows * Share of sows slaughtered

STOCK:

Demanded amount of piglets (t) = Demanded amount of piglets (t - dt) + (Demand for piglets change rate) dt

INIT:

Demanded amount of piglets = 29000000

INFLOW:

Demand for piglets change rate = IF ('Distance to carrying capacity' > 0 <<LSU/ha>>, 'Share of demand change rate for piglets' * 'Demanded amount of piglets', 0 <<animals/yr>>)

STOCK:

Piglets (t) = Piglets (t - dt) + (Piglets birth rate) dt - (Weaners growing rate) dt - (Piglets export rate) dt

INIT:

Piglets = Sows * Amount of life piglets born per sow per year

INFLOW:

Piglets birth rate = Sows * Amount of life piglets born per sow per year

OUTFLOWS:

Weaners growing rate = Piglets - Piglets export rate

Piglets export rate = Piglets * Share of exported piglets

STOCK:

Amount of life piglets born per sow per year (t) = Amount of life piglets born per sow per year (t - dt) + (The rate of change of life piglets born per sow per year) dt

INIT:

Amount of life piglets born per sow per year = 28

Time to reach target for the piglets born per sow per year = 20

Target for the piglets born per sow per year = 40

INFLOW:

The rate of change of life piglets born per sow per year = 'Difference between actual and targeted amount of piglets born per sow per year' / 'Time to reach target for the piglets born per sow per year'

STOCK:

Growing pigs (t) = Growing pigs (t - dt) + (Weaners growing rate) dt - (Weaners mortality rate) dt - (Gilts & slaughter pigs growing rate) dt

INIT:

Growing pigs = Piglets * (100 % - Share of exported piglets)

INFLOW:

Weaners growing rate = Piglets - Piglets export rate

OUTFLOWS:

Gilts & slaughter pigs growing rate = Growing pigs - Weaners mortality rate

Weaners mortality rate = Share of died weaners * Growing pigs

STOCK:

Gilts & slaughter pigs (t) = Gilts & slaughter pigs (t - dt) + (Gilts & slaughter pigs growing rate) dt - (Gilts & slaughter pigs mortality rate) dt - (Slaughtering pigs rate) dt

INIT:

Gilts & slaughter pigs = Growing pigs * 97 %

INFLOW:

Gilts & slaughter pigs growing rate = Growing pigs - Weaners mortality rate

OUTFLOWS:

Gilts & slaughter pigs growing rate = Growing pigs - Weaners mortality rate

Gilts replacing sows rate = Sows * Ratio of sows replacement

Gilts & slaughter pigs mortality rate = Share of died gilts & slaughter pigs * Gilts & slaughter pigs

Slaughtering pigs rate = Gilts & slaughter pigs - Gilts replacing sows rate - Gilts & slaughter pigs mortality rate

STOCK:

Slaughtered pigs (t) = Slaughtered pigs (t - dt) + (Slaughtering rate of pigs) dt

INIT:

Slaughtered pigs = 0

INFLOW:

Slaughtering pigs rate = Gilts & slaughter pigs - Gilts replacing sows rate - Gilts & slaughter pigs mortality rate

STOCK:

Died gilts & slaughter pigs (t) = Died gilts & slaughter pigs (t - dt) + (Gilts & slaughter pigs mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Died gilts & slaughter pigs = 0

INFLOW:

Gilts & slaughter pigs mortality rate = Share of died gilts & slaughter pigs * Gilts & slaughter pigs

STOCK:

Share of exported piglets (t) = Share of exported piglets (t - dt) + (The rate of exported piglets change) dt

INIT:

Share of exported piglets = 25

Time to reach target for the share of exported piglets = 20

Target for the share of exported piglets = 80

INFLOW:

The rate of change of life piglets born per sow per year = 'Difference between actual and targeted amount of piglets born per sow per year' / 'Time to reach target for the piglets born per sow per year'

Equation of variables

Share of sows slaughtered = 'Ratio of sows replacement' - 'Share of sows died'

Sows needed to cover the demand for piglets = DELAYPPL ('Demanded amount of piglets' / 'Amount of life piglets born per sow per year', 2<<yr>>)

Difference between actual and targeted amount of piglets born per sow per year = Target for the piglets born per sow per year – Amount of life piglets born per sow per year

Difference between actual and targeted share of exported piglets = Target for the share of exported piglets – Share of exported piglets'

S2. Cows' production submodel

In the cows' production submodel, five main stocks *Calves*, *Heifers 1-year-old*, *Adult heifers*, *Cows*, and *Bulls* are included that simulate the lifecycle of dairy cows and bulls in a conventional farm, see Figure S2 and Figure S3.

Figure 2. Stock and flow diagram for the submodel of a conventional dairy farm.

Figure 3. Stock and flow diagram for the submodel of a conventional bull fattening farm.

The major modeled variables can be divided into two flows – the newborn male calves flow going for meat production farm 14 days after birth, and the newborn female calves flow going for dairy production and later slaughtered for meat production. The production system is running to keep a constant amount of cattle. In this model, the constant number of cattle is affected only by external factors. These external changes are the expansion of the conventional cows' farms based on the historical data for the period of 2010-2018, with an average growth of 0.64 % per year [1].

Table S3 shows the names of auxiliary variables and corresponding assumed numerical values and references for cows' production submodel.

Table 3. Assumed values for auxiliary variables in cows' production submodel.

Variable in the model (correspond to the variables in Figure S2 and Figure S3)	Numerical value used	Assumption	Reference
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Cow change rate due to external factors	0.64 %/yr	Change in annual national production of milk. Historical average data for time period 2009-2018 in Denmark	[1]
Cows, (as initial value)	489672 animals	Historical data for number of conventional dairy cows in Denmark in 2009	[1]
Number of calves born per cow per year	1.0 calve/yr	1 calve per 1 cow per year	[4]
Probability of having male or female calves	50.0 %	Equal distribution among newborn male and female calves	[4]
Share of adult heifers slaughtered	2.32 %/yr	1 out of every 43 heifers slaughtered	[4]
Share of bulls died	10.0 %/yr	Equal distribution among all bulls	[4]
Share of cows died	5.0 %/yr	Equal distribution among all cows	[4]
Share of new born died	4.0 %/yr	Equal distribution among newborn male and female calves	[4]
Share of young heifers died	10.0 %/yr	For the heifers between 14 days and 1 year	[4]
Time to grow from heifer 1 year old to cow	455 days	Corresponds to 1 year and 3 months. The total amount of time to growth dairy cows is 27 months.	[4]

The corresponding equations used in the cows' production submodel are given below in Table S4.

Table 4. Equations used in the cows' production submodel.

STOCK:

Calves (t) = Calves (t - dt) + (Calves birth rate) dt - (Growing rate of heifers 0-1 year) dt - (Growing rate of male calves) dt - (New born mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Calves = Cows

INFLOW:

Calves birth rate = Cows * Number of calves born per cow per year

OUTFLOWS:

New born mortality rate = Calves * Share of new born died

Growing rate of male calves = Calves - New born mortality rate - Growing rate of heifers 0-1 year

Growing rate of heifers 0-1 year = Calves * Probability of having male or female calves - New born mortality rate / 2

STOCK:

Died new born (t) = Died new born (t - dt) + (New born mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Died new born = 0

INFLOW:

New born mortality rate = Calves * Share of new born died

STOCK:

Male calves sold to fattening unit (t) = Male calves sold to fattening unit (t - dt) + (Growing rate of male calves) dt

INIT:

Male calves sold to fattening unit = Calves * 48 %

INFLOW:

Growing rate of male calves = Growing rate of male calves = Calves – New born mortality rate –
Growing rate of heifers 0-1 year

STOCK:

Heifers 1 year old (t) = Heifers 1 year old (t – dt) + (Growing rate of heifers 0-1 year) dt – (Heifers
mortality rate) dt – (Growing rate of adult heifers) dt

INIT:

Heifers 1 year old = Calves * 48%

INFLOWS:

Growing rate of heifers 0-1 year = Calves * Probability of having male or female calves – New born
mortality rate / 2

OUTFLOWS:

Heifers mortality rate = Heifers 1 year old * Share of young heifers died

Growing rate of adult heifers = DELAYPPL ('Heifers 1 year old' – 'Heifers mortality rate', 'Time to grow
from heifers 1 year to cow')

STOCK:

Died heifers (t) = Died heifers (t – dt) + (Heifers mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Died heifers = 0

INFLOW:

Heifers mortality rate = Heifers 1 year old * Share of young heifers died

STOCK:

Adult heifers (t) = Adult heifers (t – dt) + (Growing rate of adult heifers) dt – (Adult heifers slaughtering
rate) dt – (Cow change rate due to external factors) dt – (Internal cows replacement rate) dt

INIT:

Adult heifers = Heifers 1 year old * 90 %

INFLOWS:

Growing rate of adult heifers = DELAYPPL ('Heifers 1 year old' – 'Heifers mortality rate', 'Time to grow
from heifers 1 year to cow')

OUTFLOWS:

Adult heifers slaughtering rate = Share of adult heifers slaughtered * Adult heifers

Cow change rate due to external factors = DELAYPPL (Cows * 'Share of cow changes due to external
factors', 2<<yr>>)

Internal cows' replacement rate = 'Adult heifers' – 'Adult heifers slaughtering rate' – 'Cow change rate
due to external factors'

STOCK:

Slaughtered adult heifers (t) = Slaughtered adult heifers (t – dt) + (Adult heifers slaughtering rate) dt

INIT:

Slaughtered adult heifers = 0

INFLOW:

Adult heifers slaughtering rate = Share of adult heifers slaughtered * Adult heifers

STOCK:

Cows (t) = Cows (t - dt) + (Cow change rate due to external factors) dt + (Internal cows replacement rate) dt - (Cows mortality rate) dt - (Cows slaughtering rate) dt

INIT:

Cows = 489672

INFLOWS:

Cow change rate due to external factors = DELAYPPL (Cows * 'Share of cow changes due to external factors', 2<<yr>>)

Internal cows' replacement rate = 'Adult heifers' - 'Adult heifers slaughtering rate' - 'Cow change rate due to external factors'

OUTFLOWS:

Cows mortality rate = Cows * Share of cows died

Cows slaughtering rate = Internal cows replacement rate - Cows mortality rate

STOCK:

Died cows (t) = Died cows (t - dt) + (Cows mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Died cows = 0

INFLOW:

Cows mortality rate = Cows * Share of cows died

STOCK:

Slaughtered cows (t) = Slaughtered cows (t - dt) + (Cows slaughtering rate) dt

INIT:

Slaughtered cows = 0

INFLOW:

Cows slaughtering rate = Internal cows replacement rate - Cows mortality rate

STOCK:

Bulls (t) = Bulls (t - dt) + (Purchasing rate of male calves) dt - (Bulls slaughtering rate) dt - (Bulls mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Bulls = Male calves sold to fattening unit

INFLOW:

Purchasing rate of male calves = Growing rate of male calves

OUTFLOWS:

Bulls slaughtering rate = Bulls - Bulls mortality rate

Bulls mortality rate = Share of bulls died * Bulls

STOCK:

Died bulls (t) = Died bulls (t - dt) + (Bulls mortality rate) dt

INIT:

Died bulls = 0

INFLOW:

Bulls mortality rate = Share of bulls died * Bulls

STOCK:

Slaughtered bulls (t) = Slaughtered bulls (t - dt) + (Bulls slaughtering rate) dt

INIT:

Slaughtered bulls = 0

INFLOW:

Bulls slaughtering rate = Bulls – Bulls mortality rate

Equation of variables

Total number of heifers = Adults heifers + Heifers 1 year old

Share of cows changes due to external factors = IF ('Distance to carrying capacity' > 0 <<LSU/ha>>, 0.64 <<%/yr>>, 0 <<%/yr>>)

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